
Prospects for Improving Insurance Relations in Uzbekistan

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Abstract: This article highlights the prospects for improving insurance relations in Uzbekistan, focusing on inclusive insurance and risk financing challenges. Based on analyses conducted by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), the paper provides recommendations for diversifying the existing insurance system and promoting sustainable development. It emphasizes the importance of developing a financial strategy to address natural disasters, enhancing the capabilities of insurance companies, and integrating modern technologies. The article also examines current issues within the insurance market, such as low financial coverage and inefficiency, and outlines opportunities for growth by leveraging international practices.

Key words: insurance relations, inclusive insurance, risk financing, sustainable development, natural disasters, economic security.

The insurance industry is a critical pillar of economic stability, offering mechanisms to manage risks and protect financial assets. In Uzbekistan, the need to refine and enhance insurance relationships has become increasingly evident, particularly in light of the government's strategic reforms aimed at modernizing the sector. Initiatives such as Presidential Decree PQ-4412 (2019) emphasize creating a competitive insurance market by adopting international best practices, encouraging innovation, and improving regulatory frameworks.

Uzbekistan's insurance market is characterized by its nascent development stage, with low penetration rates compared to global standards. Key challenges include insufficient public awareness of insurance benefits, limited product diversification, and underdeveloped digital infrastructure. However, significant opportunities exist, including leveraging digital technologies such as blockchain and artificial intelligence to optimize operations, enhancing the efficiency of claims processing, and broadening access to services for remote and underserved populations.

Regional comparisons reveal that Uzbekistan can benefit from the experiences of neighboring countries by fostering cross-border collaborations, organizing international forums, and integrating its insurance market into global networks. These steps are complemented by local strategies, such as improving financial literacy, incentivizing private sector investment, and introducing innovative insurance products tailored to the needs of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and individuals.

Furthermore, the emphasis on sustainable development and resilience underscores the importance of expanding insurance coverage to address climate risks and natural disasters. By aligning with global sustainable insurance initiatives and incorporating climate risk management into policies, Uzbekistan's insurance sector can play a pivotal role in the country's socio-economic transformation.

This study explores these dimensions, offering insights into the current landscape, reform priorities, and long-term development strategies for Uzbekistan's insurance market. It underscores the interplay between policy, technology, and public-private partnerships as fundamental drivers of progress in this essential economic sector.

Today, the development and implementation of a wide range of insurance services by insurance companies, capable of gaining the trust of not only domestic but also foreign clients, expanding regional insurance services, and effectively managing the financial resources of insurance companies is one of the main problems in the development of the national insurance market. This situation reflects the relevance of this topic. Insurance has been an important factor influencing the economy as an integral part of financial relations throughout the evolutionary stages of human history. In the process of globalization in the modern era, the innovative development of the insurance market is accompanied by rapid changes, which means that the theoretical and practical study of the activities of this institute is relevant. The insurance market is the main segment of any country's economy, and at the same time, it directly serves its prosperity. At the same time, it should be noted that insurance activity is a unique and widely used social phenomenon and is considered a factor of stability. Forecasting the development of the country's insurance market, in turn, has led to the need to research directions for the development of insurance activities as an institution that guarantees the protection of the interests of business entities and the population. Today, the insurance sector is the fastest-growing sector of the economy

One of the branches of industry. According to Article 3 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Insurance Activities," insurance is a relationship related to the protection of the interests of individuals and legal entities related to the creation and use of targeted funds for compensation and other payments, compensation for damage caused in the event of a specific event.

In the process of economic globalization, the insurance industry forces us to ensure the safety of enterprise property, assess financial condition, reduce financial risks, have competitive advantages, participate in integration processes, comply with global standards, and coordinated requirements for this are also increasing. This necessity requires the introduction of automated information technologies into the insurance process. A rapid and effective way to develop insurance in Uzbekistan requires the creation of software that, based on the specifics of the industry, can solve problems related to time and the human factor, meeting the requirements for ensuring increased efficiency in the activities of clients, both individuals and legal entities.

Naturally, the question arises: Why? Or insurance companies, even if there is no program! Questions and comments such as. The answers to these thoughts and questions are as follows: In Uzbekistan, almost all insurance companies have experience in automating the purchase of ready-made software products or their development with the help of their developers. In this regard, we believe that analytical analysis using "artificial intelligence," which can predict future periods using information related to the results of insurance companies, will accelerate the development of the industry.

Further reforming the national insurance market and ensuring its rapid development, introducing new types of in-demand insurance services, increasing consumer confidence in the insurance market are the most pressing issues of our time, while the negative impact of several factors on the development of life insurance requires the implementation of relevant work aimed at developing and implementing an innovative mechanism in the field of life insurance, taking into account the real realities and characteristics of our country, as well as advanced foreign experience. As a result, it should serve to ensure its long-term progressive development by further increasing the attractiveness of each potential life insurance policyholder to this type of activity. To accomplish these important tasks, it is important, first and foremost, to train personnel in the insurance industry who meet global standards and prepare them for practice, informing the population about insurance. In practice, there are many reasons hindering the development of the insurance market, one of which is the emergence of a monopoly state. In countries with a developed market economy, the number of companies operating in the same industry should be at least ten or more, with the share of one company in this market not exceeding 31 percent in the sale of insurance services, the share of two companies not exceeding 44 percent, the share of three companies not exceeding 54 percent, and the share of four companies not exceeding 64 percent. "Uzagrosugurta" and "Uzbekinvest" companies currently have more than 100 in addition to providing services and

property risks, there are also types of insurance against financial liability, agricultural and health risks. This is one of the main factors hindering the development of the insurance market Low insurance culture in the middle.

We believe that the development of qualified services of specialists such as assistant, surveyor, and adjuster, who are professional participants, is inextricably linked to the development of the industry, with clients using insurance services knowing their rights as insured, improving the infrastructure of the insurance market. The development of insurance is directly related to the level of supply and demand. The largest share of insurance premiums in the insurance sector falls on the form of compulsory insurance. Unfortunately, its market position falls on the shoulders of types of compulsory insurance.

The rate of voluntary insurance coverage is significantly lower.

In our opinion, one of the main reasons for this is that insurance organizations do not work face-to-face with clients and do not conclude an insurance contract based on the individual requirements of each client.

As a result, insurance premiums lead to a decrease in insurance revenue the low share of services in our country's GDP indicates that the quality of this type of service is not at the required level. It is no secret that there is no interest in insurance services among the population, especially very few people use voluntary insurance.

In conclusion, it should be noted that insurance has become one of the main sectors of the economy in most countries, but even more so - a material source of compensation for losses and damages affecting the population and business. The development of the insurance market in our country and the increase in people's trust in insurance services are beneficial in all respects and become a means of protection in protecting against various financial risks and risks.

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